

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. Layout of the four assay plates (N1 to N4) used to test for assimilation of nitrogen sources. A total of 24 nitrogen sources were tested. All assay plates included a positive control (basal mineral medium [BMM] with sugars [1% sucrose, 0.1% glucose and 0.1% fructose, w/v] supplemented with 0.06% w/v of peptone, first row) and a negative control (BMM with sugars but no nitrogen source, last row). Further information on these assays is provided in the main text and Table S2.

N1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A Positive control	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
B Ammonium	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
C Nitrite	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
D Nitrate	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
E Urea	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
F Betaine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
G Uracil	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
H Negative control	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○

N2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A Positive control	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
B Glycine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
C L-Leucine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
D L-Cysteine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
E L-Proline	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
F L-Asparagine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
G N-Acetyl-D-Glucosamine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
H Negative control	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○

N3	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A Positive control	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
B L-Histidine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
C L-Arginine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
D L-Glutamic acid	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
E L-Tryptophan	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
F L-Ornithine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
G Glucosamine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
H Negative control	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○

N4	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A Positive control	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
B Ethanolamine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
C Formamide	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
D Uridine	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
E Nicotinic acid	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
F Gly-Glu	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
G Gly-Asp	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
H Negative control	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○

Figure S2. Neighbor-joining (NJ) consensus tree, based on *rpoB* gene sequences, showing the relationships of the *Acinetobacter* isolates included in this study ($n = 82$). Branches correspond to the different *rpoB* sequence types (STs) that were identified based on nucleotide sequence alignments. The number of isolates belonging to each ST are indicated between square brackets. Evolutionary distances were computed using the maximum composite likelihood method, as implemented in MEGA X [1], and are in the units of number of base substitutions per site. The rate variation among sites was modeled with a gamma distribution (shape parameter = 0.28). There was a total of 859 positions in the final dataset. Node support values (bootstrap percentages, based on 100 simulations) $\geq 90\%$ are shown next to the branches. The tree was rooted with the *rpoB* gene sequence of *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus* NIPH 2245^T.

Figure S3. Maximum likelihood (ML) consensus tree, based on *rpoB* gene sequences, showing the relationships of the *Acinetobacter* isolates included in this study ($n = 82$). Branches correspond to the different *rpoB* sequence types (STs) that were identified based on nucleotide sequence alignments. The number of isolates belonging to each ST are indicated between square brackets. Evolutionary distances (number of base substitutions per site) were computed using a general time reversible substitution model with gamma distributed rate variation among sites (GTR + G model; gamma shape parameter = 0.275, as estimated by PhyML v.3.0 [2]), with four substitution rate categories, starting trees generated by BIONJ, and nearest neighbor interchange (NNI) tree search algorithm. There was a total of 859 positions in the final dataset. Node support values (bootstrap percentages, based on 100 simulations) $\geq 90\%$ are shown next to the branches. The tree was rooted with the *rpoB* gene sequence of *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus* NIPH 2245^T.

Figure S4. Bayesian inference (BI) consensus tree, based on *rpoB* gene sequences, showing the relationships of the *Acinetobacter* isolates included in this study ($n = 82$). Branches correspond to the different *rpoB* sequence types (STs) that were identified based on nucleotide sequence alignments. The number of isolates belonging to each ST or species are indicated between square brackets. The phylogenetic tree was constructed under a general time-reversible model with gamma-distributed rate variation across sites (GTR + G; shape parameter = 0.28) using MrBayes v3.2.6 [3] as implemented on the CIPRES Science Gateway V. 3.3 [4]. Four chains were run twice (chain temperature = 0.2; sample frequency = 100) until average standard deviation of split frequencies was below 0.01. A 50% majority-rule consensus tree was calculated after discarding the first 25% of the trees to yield the final Bayesian estimate of phylogeny. There was a total of 859 positions in the final dataset. Node support values (BI posterior probabilities) ≥ 0.9 are shown next to the branches. The tree was rooted with the *rpoB* gene sequence of *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus* NIPH 2245^T.

Figure S5. Beanplots showing the results obtained in the nitrogen assimilation tests performed on *Acinetobacter* isolates of different *rpoB* clade affiliations. The shape of the beans represents the distribution of growth score values. Black thick lines indicate the average index value for each *rpoB* clade, the dotted line that among all clades. AA: *Acinetobacter apis* ($n = 1$), AB: *Acinetobacter boissieri* ($n = 9$), ABT: *Acinetobacter bareti* ($n = 2$), AN: *Acinetobacter nectaris* ($n = 56$), AP: *Acinetobacter pollinis* ($n = 14$).

Figure S6. Beanplots showing the results obtained in the nitrogen assimilation tests performed on *Acinetobacter* isolates according to their sample type of origin (floral nectar, $n = 57$; or insect, $n = 25$). The shape of the beans represents the distribution of growth score values. Black thick lines indicate the average index value for each sample type, the dotted line that among all groups.

Figure S7. Beanplots showing the results obtained in the nitrogen assimilation tests performed on *Acinetobacter* isolates according to their country of origin (Belgium, $n = 19$; Japan, $n = 1$; Spain, $n = 20$; or USA, $n = 42$). The shape of the beans represents the distribution of growth score values. Black thick lines indicate the average index value for each location, the dotted line that among all groups.

Figure S8. Beanplots showing the distribution of nutrient assimilation (NA) indices across *Acinetobacter* isolates from different *rpoB* clades (A), sample types (B) or countries (C). The shape of the beans represents the distribution of growth score values. Black thick lines indicate the average index value for each group under analysis, the dotted line that among all groups. *rpoB* clades: AA, *Acinetobacter apis* ($n = 1$); AB, *Acinetobacter boissieri* ($n = 9$); ABT, *Acinetobacter bareti* ($n = 2$); AN, *Acinetobacter nectaris* ($n = 56$); or AP: *Acinetobacter pollinis* ($n = 14$). Sample types: floral nectar ($n = 57$) or insect ($n = 25$). Countries: Belgium ($n = 19$), Japan ($n = 1$), Spain ($n = 20$) or USA ($n = 42$).

Figure S9. Correlograms of the nitrogen assimilation capabilities of the *Acinetobacter* isolates analyzed in this study ($n = 82$). Colors show the correlation (Spearman's ρ) between growth scores (*left*) or phylogenetically independent contrasts (*right*) for each pair of traits. Significant correlations are shown in the lower triangle.

Figure S10. Scree plots obtained by conventional principal component analysis (PCA, *above*) and phylogenetic PCA (*below*) of nitrogen assimilation data from the *Acinetobacter* isolates characterized in this study ($n = 82$).

Figure S11. Bar plots representing the loadings of each factor on the first two components (PC1 and PC2) obtained by conventional principal component analysis (PCA, *right*) and phylogenetic PCA (*left*) of nitrogen assimilation data obtained for the *Acinetobacter* isolates characterized in this study ($n = 82$). Green and red bars refer to positive and negative loadings, respectively. Codes of nitrogen assimilation tests are as in Table S2.

Figure S12. Scores plots showing the distribution of *Acinetobacter* isolates according to the first two components obtained by conventional principal component analysis (PCA) of the covariance matrix of nitrogen assimilation data. The plot corresponding to the classic PCA and the phylogenetic PCA are shown in the *left* and *right* panel, respectively. Colors of points and the 68% data concentration ellipses denote different “microenvironments” of origin, i.e. body part of insects (honey crop, $n = 11$; gut, $n = 3$; or mouth, $n = 11$) or plant family (*Lamiaceae*, $n = 5$; *Onagraceae*, $n = 11$; *Phrymaceae*, $n = 6$; *Plantaginaceae*, $n = 8$; *Scrophulariaceae*, $n = 13$; or other, $n = 14$).

Figure S13. A, B and C: Scores plots showing the distribution of *Acinetobacter* isolates according to the first two components obtained by conventional principal component analysis (PCA) of the correlation matrix of nitrogen assimilation data. These principal components explained 54.7% of the total variance in the original dataset. Colors of points and the 68% data concentration ellipses denote different *rpoB* clades (panel A), sample sources (B) or countries of origin (C). D: PCA loadings plot, where each arrow represents the loadings on the first two principal components for one factor (growth performance on a given nitrogen source). Abbreviations: AA: *Acinetobacter apis* ($n = 1$), AB: *Acinetobacter boissieri* ($n = 9$), ABT: *Acinetobacter bareti* ($n = 2$), AN: *Acinetobacter nectaris* ($n = 56$), AP: *Acinetobacter pollinis* ($n = 14$). Codes of nitrogen assimilation tests are as in Table S2.

Figure S14. A, B and C: Scores plots showing the distribution of *Acinetobacter* isolates according to the first two components obtained by phylogenetic principal component analysis (PCA) of the correlation matrix of nitrogen assimilation data. These principal components explained 56.7% of the total variance in the original dataset. Colors of points and the 68% data concentration ellipses denote different *rpoB* clades (panel A), sample sources (B) or countries of origin (C). D: phylogenetic PCA loadings plot, where each arrow represents the loadings on the first two principal components for one factor (growth performance on a given nitrogen source). Abbreviations: AA: *Acinetobacter apis* ($n = 1$), AB: *Acinetobacter boissieri* ($n = 9$), ABT: *Acinetobacter bareti* ($n = 2$), AN: *Acinetobacter nectaris* ($n = 56$), AP: *Acinetobacter pollinis* ($n = 14$). Codes of nitrogen assimilation tests are as in Table S2.

Figure S15. contMap trees mapping observed and estimated average growth scores in the different nitrogen assimilation assays performed in this study onto the edges of the neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree built from *rpoB* sequence types (STs). The number of isolates belonging to each ST is indicated in Figure 1.

Glycine

L-Leucine

L-Cysteine

L-Proline

L-Asparagine

N-Acetyl-D-glu.

L-Histidine

L-Arginine

L-Glutamic acid

L-Tryptophan

L-Ornithine

Glucosamine

Ethanolamine

Formamide

Uridine

Nicotinic acid

Gly-Glu

Gly-Asp

Figure S16. contMap tree mapping observed and estimated average nitrogen assimilation (NA) indices onto the edges of the neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree built from *rpoB* sequence types (STs). The number of isolates belonging to each ST is indicated in Figure 1.

REFERENCES

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